

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE WAX FROM SUGARCANE.

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Sugarcane wax extracted from the press-mud of a sulphitation factory has been found to contain 43.7% of acids and 53.0% of non-saponifiable material. By the usual method of ester fractionation under a reduced pressure, the component acids have been found to be resin acid (4.5%), caproic acid (0.6%), palmitic acid (22.7%), stearic acid (22.4%), oleic acid (41.5%) and arachidic acid (3.3%). The non-saponifiable material has been resolved into primary alcohols, secondary alcohols, and paraffin fractions by treating it with phthalic anhydride. The non-saponifiables consist of about 80% primary alcohol *n*-triacontanol or myricyl alcohol, about 10% is a mixture of sterols, from which brassica, stigma and sitosterols have been isolated by the fractional crystallisation of their bromination products and about 5% of an aliphatic paraffin, *n*-pentatriacontane (C₃₅H₇₂). The wax does not contain any dibasic acid or oxy-acid.

Sugar cane wax was observed by Avequin (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1840, ii, 75, 214) to be a mixture of different bodies, occurring on the exterior of cane. In some varieties it may amount to about 0.05% on cane and in some it might be nil. When the cane is crushed the major portion of this wax goes along with the juice. Its presence in the juice is as much detrimental to the manufacture of sugar as of any other non-sugars. During the process of clarification the wax is precipitated and goes along with the press-cake. The chemical nature of the wax extracted from press-cake has been studied by various investigators. There have been two reasons to initiate this investigation; the first to eliminate it as completely as possible from the clarified juice and the second to utilise it as a commercial commodity.

Wijnberg (*Deuts. Zuckerind.*, 1909, 34, 629; *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1909, 28, 991) studied the composition of cane-wax and also patented the process for its recovery from the press-cake for industrial use (B.P. 25669 of Nov., 1910). He found that 70% of the wax consist of the glycerides of oleic, linolic, palmitic and stearic acids along with hydroxy-acids, resin acids, phytosterols and colouring matters and the remaining 30% contain 45% of myricyl alcohol, 35% of a non-primary crystalline alcohol and at least one more crystalline substance, poor in oxygen (m.p. 88-90°) corresponding to C₃₃H₆₆O.

Bosz (*Arch. Suikerind in Nederlandsch-Indie*, 1920, 28, No. 25, 974) examined the wax, extracted from the press-cake of a sugar factory in Java. He could not get any positive indication towards the presence of sterols when he applied the ordinary colour reaction to the wax. He

identified stearic, palmitic, caproic and formic acids along with myricyl alcohol. He does not mention any unsaturated compound in the wax.

While the present work was in progress Tetsuo Mitsui (*J. Agric. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1937, **13**, 494) obtained phytosterols from the sugarcane wax and also suggested that it could be utilised as a starting material for the preparation of hormones. He has not mentioned much about the nature of the phytosterols.

Recently a good deal of work has been done on the plant and insect waxes and a number of ketones, ketonic alcohols and paraffins have been isolated. Cane-wax as well might contain some such compounds which might have escaped the observation of the previous workers. It was considered desirable to re-examine the wax and identify the individual components with the help of the more recent methods adopted for the study of other fats and waxes. The composition of the component acids has been determined by the usual ester fractionation method of Hilditch *et. al.* (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1927, **46**, 1722) and the non-saponifiable constituents have been studied by phthalic anhydride method of Chibnal and Piper (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, **25**, 2095).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

In March 1937, fully riped cane (Co. 213) was crushed in the Sri Ram Sugar factory, Ltd., Bobbili.* The juice was clarified by the double sulphitation process, when a clear juice practically free from wax was obtained. The scum was maintained at 7° R. W. and kieselguhr was added to aid the filtration. The cake, so obtained, was dried up at 100°, powdered and extracted with benzene which was found in a preliminary experiment to be the most suitable solvent. The wax was dark green in colour and its physical and chemical constants are compared with those observed by the other workers.

TABLE I.

	Wijnberg.	Lewkowitsch.	Bosz.	Present workers.
Sap. value	167·9	81·2	177·0	133·5
Iodine „	60·0	87·7	—	31·5
Acid „	38·6	11·9	47·3	23·4
Acetyl „	55·6	—	—	89·6
Non-saponifiables	58·8	69·1	—	43·7
Melting points	55·79°	58·59°	60-62°	68·7°

* We express our gratitude to the mill authorities for allowing us this facility.

The Component Acids of the Wax.

The crude wax (250 g.) was purified by boiling successively with 5% solution of sodium sulphite, 3% solution of hydrochloric acid and finally a number of times with distilled water till free from the mineral acids and other inorganic matters. It was dried at 90° under reduced pressure. The dry wax (200 g.) was dissolved in benzene (1000 c.c.) and saponified by boiling with an excess of 5*N*-alcoholic caustic soda. After distilling off the solvent the soap was mixed with silver sand and fried till it was friable. The non-saponifiables were extracted from the soap with acetone and petroleum ether consecutively but as the soap was found to contain some non-saponifiables, it was converted into calcium soap and extracted with a little dry benzene. The small quantity of soap extracted with the non-saponifiables was recovered and added to the main bulk of soap by washing the ether solution of the non-saponifiables with water. Acids were liberated from the soap by boiling with glacial acetic acid, 106 g. of the acids (sap. equiv., 294; I.V., 39.5) and 87.5 g. of non-saponifiables (I. V., 10.5) were obtained. The rest were water-soluble and steam-volatile materials.

Separation of Solid and Liquid Acids.

The solid and liquid acids were separated by the Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) with a slight modification of recrystallising the sticky alcohol-insoluble lead salts from ether.

Fractions obtained from 30 g. of acids (sap. equiv., 294; I. V., 39.5) are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Fractions.	Quantity.	Sap. Equiv.	I. V.
A. From the lead salts, soluble in alcohol and ether	12.2 g.	279	80.2
E. From the lead salts, soluble in ether	8.5	302	18.9
S. From the lead salts, insoluble in ether and alcohol	9.2	314	14.8

In order to separate any dibasic or oxy-acid, all these fractions were treated separately with light boiling petroleum ether, but no insoluble matter was obtained. This proves the absence of dibasic and oxy-acids.

The acid from A (2 g.) was oxidised with potassium permanganate (2 g.) in alkaline solution at about 0° according to the method of Lapworth

and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1678). The saturated acid, extracted from the product of oxidation by petroleum ether, was identified to be palmitic acid, m.p. 61°, unchanged when mixed with an authentic sample. In the oxidation product no tetrahydroxy nor any hexahydroxy acid could be found; only dihydroxystearic acid, m.p. 120° (either alone or mixed with an authentic sample of $\Delta^{9:10}$ -dihydroxy acid) was detected. The only unsaturated fatty acid in this wax is oleic acid.

From the acid fraction (E) palmitic, stearic and oleic acids were identified.

The acids identified from (S) were oleic and stearic acids along with archidic acid, m.p. 75° and equiv., 307.5 (calc. for $C_{20}H_{40}O_2$: Equiv., 312).

The Estimation of Resin Acids.

Twitchell's method (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1891, 10, 804) was adopted for the estimation of the resin acids and their separation from the fatty acids. A solution of mixed acids (65 g.) in absolute alcohol (800 c.c.) was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas and allowed to stand for 3 hours at the room temperature and then boiled with distilled water till an oily layer was obtained. This oily layer was taken up in ether, and washed free from hydrochloric acid. An aliquot part of this ethereal solution was taken up with an equal volume of neutral alcohol and the amount of resin acid (4.5% on the total acids) which remained unesterified, was calculated by titrating it against a *N*. 2-solution of caustic potash. The rest of the ethyl ester of fatty acids was washed neutral with sodium carbonate solution and water and fractionated.

Fractional Distillation of the Ethyl Esters.

50 G. of neutral ethyl esters of the fatty acids (sap. equiv., 306.0 and I. V., 37.5) were fractionated from a packed column Willstätter's bulb under a pressure of 0.2 mm. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Fraction.	B. p.	Wt.	Sap. Equiv.	I. V.	Acids identified.
1.	110-130°	9.0 g.	282.2	38.0	Palmitic and oleic.
2.	132°	23.5	298.8	49.5	Palmitic, stearic and oleic.
3.	168°	3.0	310.3	62.8	„
4.	170°	3.0	319.5	38.4	Stearic, archidic and oleic.
5.	Residue	10.4	332.0	6.5	Stearic and archidic.

* The residue contained 3.02% of non-saponifiable materials of corrected values of sap. equiv., 322.0 and I. V., 6.7.

Identification of Caproic Acid.

The boiling point and the equivalent of the fraction 1 were too low for the ethyl esters of a hexadecenoic acid. No acid lower than palmitic could be crystallised out. Some lower and steam-volatile acid must be in this wax. A good lot of it might have escaped at the time of the liberation of the acids. Therefore, 80 g. of the crude wax were saponified and the soap was splitted up by the addition of an excess of dilute sulphuric acid. It was distilled in steam till no more acid was coming in the distillate and 3 litres of distillate were collected. An excess of sodium hydroxide was added and the volume was boiled down to 400 c.c. The steam-volatile non-saponifiable materials such as myricyl alcohol and a little of essential oil, smelling like geraniol, were extracted with ether and the soap was splitted up by adding dilute hydrochloric acid, 0.63 g. of acid being obtained (0.1126 g. of the Ba salt gave 0.0421 g. of Ba. Found: M.W., 115.05. Calc. for $C_6H_{12}O_2$: M.W., 116.0). The distillate did not respond to any test for formic acid.

Composition of the Acidic Component of the Wax.

TABLE IV.

Acids.	Wt. of fatty acids.	Wt. of total acids.	% on the wax.
Caproic	0.7%	0.6%	0.3
Palmitic	29.0	27.7	14.7
Stearic	23.4	22.4	11.8
Oleic	43.5	41.5	22.0
Archidic	3.4	3.3	1.8
Resinous acid	...	4.5	2.4

Disruptive Oxidation of the Unsaturated Acid.

15 G. of the ethyl ester (sap. equiv., 310.5 and I.V., 81.5), obtained by the fractional crystallisation of the lead salts of the acids of fractions 1 and 2 (Table III) were oxidised by potassium permanganate in acetone solution according to the methods of Armstrong and Hilditch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, **44**, 447). In the product of oxidation azelaic acid (m.p. and mixed m.p. 105°) and nonolic acid (equiv., 160) were obtained.

The Non-saponifiables of the Wax

The crude dark coloured wax (300 g.) was resolved into two fractions by boiling thrice, with two litres of 25 % alcohol and filtering the solution hot each time. As some of the non-saponifiables were steam-volatile, the method of purification adopted in the acidic portion had to be given up. The alcohol-soluble portion had in it most of the green colour of the wax which was decolourised by boiling for 1 hour with animal charcoal in alcohol solution and filtering hot; 135 g. of clear white wax were obtained. The residue was dissolved in benzene and decolourised with animal charcoal, when 145 g. of light brown wax were obtained. Both these fractions were examined separately. The general scheme of separation is given in the following table.

TABLE V.

Wax A.—The alcohol-soluble wax fraction A (125 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (1500 c.c.) and saponified by boiling with alcoholic caustic potash (12%, 1200 c.c.) for 8 hours. After complete saponification the potassium soap was converted into calcium soap by adding 2 litres of 8% solution of calcium chloride in alcohol and boiling for another 2 hours. It was filtered hot. The non-saponifiable materials were separated from the soap in the

filtrate. As the calcium soap still contained some non-saponifiables, it was extracted successively with alcohol, acetone and benzene. The residues of all these extracts were added to the main filtrate, which was again saponified with an excess of alcoholic caustic potash. All the calcium soap was converted into potassium soap and the precipitate of calcium hydroxide was filtered off. The solvent was evaporated off from the filtrate. The residue was taken up in ether and washed with water in order to make it free from soap, glycerine and other water-soluble matters. The portion (R_1), least soluble in ether, was crystallised out and identified to be myricyl alcohol. The residue A_1 from the mother-liquor was subjected to the phthalic anhydride treatment.

Fraction A_1 .—The fraction A_1 (20 g.) was mixed with phthalic anhydride (20 g.), pyridine (8 c.c.) and refluxed at a temperature of 125° for 18 hours. The resulting mass was poured while hot into a dilute solution of hydrochloric acid to remove pyridine. The black solid layer, which was obtained on cooling, was boiled a number of times with water to remove the excess of phthalic anhydride. It was then dissolved in ether (600 c.c.) and the ethereal solution was treated with an excess of slightly warm aqueous solution of sodium carbonate (4 %). A grey precipitate of the sodium phthalate of primary alcohol was thrown down, which could not be separated easily. The whole mixture was separated by centrifuging into three separate layers, viz., ether layer, aqueous layer and the solid layer. The solid and aqueous layers were extracted again with ether and the extracts were added to the main ether solution. Solvent was evaporated off from this ether solution and the residue was taken up in alcohol. All these three fractions were saponified with 20 % alcoholic caustic potash for 18 hours and the non-saponifiables A_{11} , A_{12} and A_{13} were extracted from the soaps in usual manner.

The Fraction A_{11} .—This fraction contained the primary alcohol which after crystallisation from benzene-alcohol mixture (1 : 1) melted at 85° . It has been further identified along with the other primary alcoholic portion of the wax and found to be myricyl alcohol. From the mother-liquor a slimy yellow liquid was obtained, whose quantity was too small for identification.

Fraction A_{12} .—The sodium phthalate of this portion was soluble in water. It was crystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture (1 : 1) and acetone-methyl alcohol mixture (1 : 3) when it melted at $133-134^\circ$ (not sharp). It gave all colour tests (cf. Liebermann-Burchard, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1890, I, 25 ; Salkowski, *Z. physiol.*, 1908, 57, 523 ; Rosenheim, *Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 47) for sterols and hence it was a mixture of sterols.

Fraction A₁₃.—It was crystallised from acetone and methyl alcohol mixture (1 : 3) when it melted at 135°, m. p. rising up to 137·5° after two crystallisations from the same solvent. Just like A₁₂, it gave all the tests for sterols.

Wax B (Alcohol-insoluble).—The alcohol-insoluble wax B (120 g.) was saponified and the non-saponifiable was separated in the same way as A, excepting that benzene, instead of alcohol was used for dissolving the wax. From this fraction the portion R₂, least soluble in ether, was separated out and it was identified to be myricyl alcohol.

Fraction B₁.—The ether-soluble non-saponifiable from B was separated into primary alcohol, secondary alcohol and paraffin by treating with phthalic anhydride. In this case four fractions were obtained. The last fraction B₁₄, separated as an alcohol-insoluble substance when the sodium phthalate of the secondary alcohol was dissolved in alcohol. According to Chibnal *et. al.* (*loc. cit.*) it could be a paraffin or a ketone.

Fraction B₁₁.—This fraction on crystallisation from benzene-alcohol mixture was found to be myricyl alcohol.

Fractions B₁₂ and B₁₃.—Just like the fractions A₁₂ and A₁₃ they were found to be a mixture of sterols.

Fraction B₁₄.—This fraction was treated with phthalic anhydride again. After the elimination of the small quantity of primary and secondary alcohols, it was found to be a light powder, m.p. 74-75° (shrinking at 73°). It did not respond to any test for a ketone. It was inactive towards most of the reagents. This is a characteristic property of higher aliphatic paraffins (*cf.* Piper, Chibnal, Hopkins and Smith, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 2072) which have a transition point as well as a melting point. [Found: C, 85·3; H, 14·3; M. W. (cryoscopic), 498. Calc. for C₃₅H₇₂: C, 85·44; H, 14·66 per cent. M.W., 49·2). All the properties agree with those for *n*-pentatriacontane.

Myricyl Alcohol.—The fractions R₁, R₂, A₁₁ and B₁₁ were found to be similar, melting at 85-86° and there was no depression when the crystallised product of any of them was mixed with the other. They were mixed up and the mixture was converted into an acetate (m.p. 75-76°) and a benzoate (m. p. 69-70°). By fusing it with soda lime at 250° melissic acid (C₃₀H₆₀O₂, m.p. 91°) was obtained. The acetate of this alcohol had the saponification equivalent of 482. (Calc. for myricyl acetate C₃₂H₆₄O₂: 480). It is obvious that this primary alcohol is *n*-triacontanol or myricyl alcohol (C₃₀H₆₂O).

Individual Sterols from the Mixture.—The fractions A₁₂, A₁₃, B₁₂ and B₁₃ were found to be similar. No pure product could be identified from

any of them. All these fractions were mixed up and the mixture had an optical rotation (in chloroform solution) $[\alpha]_D^{26}$, -39.8° . It was converted into an acetate by boiling with acetic anhydride and 3 g. of this acetate were dissolved in ether (30 c. c.) and brominated according to the method of Windaus and Hauth (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4378). The first crop of crystals was recrystallised from chloroform-alcohol mixture (1:1), when shining rhombic crystals were obtained. It decomposed at 205° . These crystals when debrominated gave crystals of the acetate as six-sided leaflets, m.p. $152-53^\circ$. There was no depression in the m.p. when it was mixed with an authentic sample of brassica sterol acetate obtained from mustard seed oil.

The mother-liquor was concentrated and left to crystallise at a temperature of 3° . Some more hexagonal crystals were obtained, which on recrystallisation were found to decompose at 203 . Probably it contained a small quantity of tetrabromo-brassica sterol acetate as well. On debromination the acetate of this sterol was obtained, m.p. 140° . The sterol obtained by the saponification of the acetate was needles, m. p. $168-69^\circ$. It had got all the characteristics of stigmasterol.

From the mother-liquor, after separation of the two crops of crystals of the bromoacetates of these two sterols, the solvent was evaporated off. The residue was debrominated. The acetate, when crystallised from absolute alcohol, melted at 134° and the sitosterol obtained on saponification melted at 143° .

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